

Study on Diagnosis and Prediction of Liver Disease Based on Machine Learning

¹Miss M. G. Muthal, ²Dr. A. B. Gadicha

Abstract— In the healthcare industry, machine learning is critical. It's crucial in computer-assisted treatment. Computer-Aided Diagnosis is a rapidly growing and active research area in the pharmaceutical business. The present generation of computer vision experts guarantees improved disease detection and analysis precision. Systems are given the ability to think through learning and producing data. This approach allows computers to learn on their own without having to be explicitly trained by a developer. Machine Learning Algorithms are used to categorize data sets using a variety of methods. They are Reinforcement, Deep Learning, Supervised, Unsupervised, and Semi-Supervised techniques. The main aim of this paper is to give a comparative analysis of supervised learning algorithms in the medicinal area and a few of the techniques utilized as a part of liver disease prediction.

Keywords— Machine Learning, Computer-Aided Diagnosis, Supervised, Unsupervised, And Semi-Supervised, Reinforcement, Deep Learning Algorithms, Liver Disease

I. INTRODUCTION

The liver is the main, most powerful organ in the human body Weighed approximately three pounds. The right and left extensions of the liver are two massive regions. The pancreas, together with portions of the liver and internal tract, is located beneath the liver. To consume, and processes the food, the liver, and these organs collaborate. The liver's primary function is to remove toxic compounds from the digestive tract into the bloodstream before they reach the entire body [1].

Liver illness is among the most lethal disorders on the planet. Fatty liver, liver fibrosis, cirrhosis, hepatitis, and viruses are the most common consequences of liver problems [2]. Figure 1 depicts the steps of liver failure: during the first phase, a normal liver becomes fatty because of cholesterol level in the body has been increased, after months or several years, the fatty liver becomes liver fibrosis, and finally, cirrhosis is the critical step of liver failure.

Manuscript Received Feb 5, 2022; Revised 25 Feb, 2022 and Published on March 15, 2022

Miss M. G. Muthal, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, P.R. Pote Patil College of Engineering & Management Amravati, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: mohinimuthal@gmail.com

Dr. A. B. Gadicha, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, P.R. Pote Patil College of Engineering & Management Amravati, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: ajjugadicha@gmail.com

Figure 1: Steps of Liver Damage

Although when tissue samples have been significantly affected in the initial phases of liver illness, it is extremely challenging to detect, which is why so many medical doctors consistently failed to recognize the condition. This can lead to improper medicine and therapy; therefore, early discovery is critical to saving the patient's life [5].

II. MACHINE LEARNING

ML [4] is a subset of AI concerned with creating an adaptable computer-based system that can train from data input or its previous problem-solving expertise to enhance its capability and effectiveness. AI is the study of how to program computers to perform tasks that humans now perform effectively. Competency and effectiveness are two characteristics of learning.

Figure 2: Categories of Machine Learning

A. Supervised Learning

The term implies that trained sequences are supervised in terms of their labeling. The classifier is what the learning algorithm is all about. The training dataset contains patterns as well as labels, whereas the test set contains only forms without labels. We can develop classifiers using machine learning classification methods, such as DT, RF, XGBoosts, SVM, LR, and so on, with fed a training dataset as input. The unlabeled patterns are labeled using the sample data as input to the classifiers [3].

Figure 3: Steps of the Machine Learning process

Gathering the dataset is the initial phase. Datasets can be obtained via various repository, which contains various datasets. Key characteristics in the database are discovered using simple approaches such as previously or from data provided by professionals. Data pre-processing procedures are required since the datasets contain distorted data and characteristic scores.

Data preprocessing is the next step. Attribute identification minimizes sample size and allows a data mining method to operate and perform successfully with extremely huge

datasets. The technique of detecting and deleting as many unnecessary and duplicate characteristics as desirable is known as the selection of features [6].

Selection of ML algorithm: In the procedure of selecting the best possible machine learning algorithm for measuring the accuracy level is a vital phase. The assessor for the classification is dependent on accuracy.

The effectiveness of ML classifiers is calculated using a minimum 3 strategies. The 2/3 and 1/3 rule, cross-validation, and leaving one out cross-validation are only a few examples [7].

We must repeat the earlier step of the ML process if the mistake ratio is really large. By continuing the procedure, a range of variables must be investigated and corrected.

B. Unsupervised learning

Unsupervised machine learning, in a contrast to supervised learning, is nothing more than clustering with no labels. Investigators expect to identify an undiscovered but beneficial category or item by using these unsupervised techniques [8].

Clustering is a term used to describe unsupervised learning. Clustering is ubiquitous, and a plethora of clustering techniques have been created to handle a variety of issues in a variety of industries. Unfortunately, no single clustering approach can be employed to tackle every challenge. Developing a cohesive structure for understanding regarding at a technological basis has been exceedingly challenging, and profoundly varied methods to clustering [9]. Clustering techniques are divided into 5 groups, as per AK Jain [8], partitioning, hierarchical, density-based, grid-based, and model-based approaches.

C. Semi-Supervised Learning

Some other sort of ML is semi-supervised learning. It's somewhere between supervised (training input data) and unsupervised learning (training input data without label). When small amounts of labeled data and a huge quantity of unlabeled data, such an algorithm works exceptionally well [10].

D. Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning is a sort of ML technique that allows software components and machines to autonomously determine the best behavior in a given situation in order to maximize performance. For the agent to learn its behavior, it needs only simple monetary information. A reinforcing signal [11] is a term used to describe this procedure.

III. RELATED WORK

Machine learning algorithms can provide professionals with important facts, actual information, and analytic tools about a patient's condition, laboratory testing reports, blood pressure, family background, clinical study data, and others. Machine learning techniques are now widely used for obtaining and analyzing medical data in order to create

customized prediction models that improve diagnosis efficiency in any given disorder. Furthermore, just a number of machine learning studies have looked into liver illnesses, despite the fact that this disease is rapidly spreading and becomes one of the leading causes of death in certain nations [12].

To develop a hybrid classifier framework for HCV diagnosis, Omar S. Soliman et. al. [13] utilized two algorithms: the Particle Swarm Optimization approach and the Least Squares Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM). The researchers extracted feature vectors using the Principal Component Analysis technique. The Modified-PSO Algorithm is performed to find the best LS-SVM parametric settings. On the targeted HCV data set from UCI repository sources, the suggested model was performed and tested. According to the empirical findings, the suggested approach outperformed some other approaches in terms of efficiency.

Mold Abdar et al. [14] suggested a computer-based detection technique for liver illness prediction utilizing novel tree-based methods, the C5.0 algorithm, and the Chi-square Automatic Interaction Detector (CHAID) algorithm. The developers of this suggested protocol employed the C5.0 algorithm with the Boosting methodology to get the maximum efficiency and rule generation on the liver problems database.

Sadiyah Noor Novita Alifisahrin et. al. [15] applied three techniques, which are Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, and NBTree algorithms for the diagnosis of liver disease. They have an im- implemented classification model and obtained

the highest accuracy by using the NB Tree algorithm. The authors concluded that the Naive Bayes algorithm gives the fastest computation time followed by the Decision Tree and NB Tree algorithm and also proved that several classification rules of the NB Tree algorithm are simpler than the number of classification rules produced by the Decision Tree algorithm.

For the diagnosis of liver illness, Bendi Venkata Ramana developed five categorization systems. On two distinct methods of liver large datasets, the authors used Naive Bayes classification, C 4.5 Decision Tree, Back Propagation, K-Nearest Neighbor, and Support Vector Machine algorithms on BUPA liver illness data and India Liver Patient Data (ILPD). The various techniques are evaluated in regards to performance categorization effectiveness in terms of Accuracy, Precision, Sensitivity, and Specificity in categorizing liver patient databases in this research. Furthermore, used the K-Nearest Neighbor and Support Vector Machine methods to get the maximum performance [16].

Sumedh Sontakke et al. [17] suggested two ways for classifying severe liver disease: one uses a clinical strategy to detect, while the other uses a genetic technique. Artificial Neural Networks and Multi-Layer Perceptrons are used in the suggested methodology for Micro-Array Analysis. Researchers employed two strategies to enhance the performance of two techniques for classifying liver disease: Back Propagation and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The Back-Propagation method [17] was used by the researchers to get the maximum performance.

Table 1: Summary of related work for Liver Disease Diagnosis and Prediction

Ref No.	Method/Techniques	Dataset Used	Findings	Accuracy
14	C5.0 algorithm CHAID algorithm	UCI	Boosting techniques in the C5.0 algorithm leads to increased accuracy and speed in creating rules	93.75 65
15	Decision tree Naive Bayes, NB Tree	UCI	Obtained the highest accuracy by using the NB Tree algorithm	66.14 56.14 67.01
16	Naive Bayes classification C 4.5 Decision Tree, Back Propagation, K-Nearest Neighbor, SVM	BUPA, (UCI) [20]	KNN, Backpropagation is giving better results with all the feature set combinations.	96.27 96.93 97.47 97.07
17	SVM Back Propagation	UCI	Backpropagation is giving highest accuracy	71 73.2
18	Decision Tree	Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology of Kasralainy Hospital of Cairo University	Achieved the Highest accuracy rate by using a Decision Tree algorithm	93.7
19	PSO GA MReg ADT	Egyptian National Committee for control of viral Hepatitis Data Base, NTP HCV Patients data (39,567)	ADT Model achieved the Highest Accuracy rate	66.4 69.6 69.1 84.4

CONCLUSION

This study gives an overview of some of the most current

machine learning techniques for detecting and diagnosing liver disease. Several supervised methods, such as KNN,

Decision Tree, Random Forest, and SVM, give improved effectiveness in the diagnosis of liver disorders, according to the investigation.

- [19] BUPA Liver Disorders Dataset. UCI repository of machine learning databases.
[ftp://ftp.ics.uci.edu/pub/machinelearningdatabases/liverdisorders/bupa.data](http://ftp.ics.uci.edu/pub/machinelearningdatabases/liverdisorders/bupa.data), last accessed: 07 October 2010.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. M. Gilligan, D. M. Venesy dan F. D. Gordon, 100 Questions & Answers About Liver, Heart, and Kidney Transplantation A Lahey Clinic Guide, United States of America: Jones & Bartlett Learning, 2011.
- [2] Mohlman, M.K., Saleh, D.A., Ezzat, S. et al. Viral transmission risk factors in an Egyptian population with high hepatitis C prevalence. *BMC Public Health* 15, 1030 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-015-2369-y>.
- [3] Uddin, S., Khan, A., Hossain, M. et al. Comparing different supervised machine learning algorithms for disease prediction. *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak* 19, 281 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-019-1004-8>.
- [4] S. A. Gonzalez dan E. B. Keeffe, "Acute liver failure, "Dalam Handbook of Liver Disease Third Edition, Philadelphia, Elsevier, 2012, pp. 20-33
- [5] Lianxi Wang, Shengyi Jiang, Siyu Jiang, "A feature selection method via analysis of relevance, redundancy, and interaction", *Expert Systems with Applications*, Volume 183, 30 November 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2021.115365>
- [6] P Viswanath, K Rajesh, C. Lavanya, and Y C A Padmanabha Reddy, "A Selective Incremental Approach for Transductive Nearest Neighbour Classification. Proceedings of IEEE International Conference of RAICS-2011.pp (221-226), 2011
- [7] Alqahtani, A.; Ali, M.; Xie, X.; Jones, M.W. Deep Time-Series Clustering: A Review. *Electronics* 2021, 10, 3001. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10233001>.
- [8] J. Kleinberg, "An impossibility theorem for clustering," in Proc. 2002 Conf. Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, vol. 15, 2002, pp. 463-470.
- [9] Bhowmick, Kiran & Narvekar, Meera. (2019). A Comprehensive Study and Analysis of Semi-Supervised Learning Techniques. *International Journal of Engineering and Technical Research*. 8. 810-816.
- [10] Kaur, Amanpreet & Gourav, Kumar. (2020). A Study of Reinforcement Learning Applications & Its Algorithms. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*. 9.
- [11] Bendi Venkata Ramana, "Efficiency measure of Machine Learning Algorithms on Liver Disease Diagnosis", *Psychology and Education* (2021) 57(5): 375-383.
- [12] Omar S. Soliman, Eman Abo Elhamd, Classification of Hepatitis C Virus using Modified Particle Swarm Optimization and Least Squares Support Vector Machine, *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 5, Issue 3, March-2014 122
- [13] Moloud Abdar, Mariam Zomorodi- Moghadam, Resul Das, I-Hsien Ting "Performance analysis of classification algorithms on early detection of Liver disease", DOI: 10.1016/j.eswa. 2016.08.065
- [14] Sadiyah Noor Novita Alifisahrin, Teddy Mantoro "Data Mining Techniques for optimization of liver disease classification." *Electronic ISBN: 978-1-4799-2758-6 DOI: 10.1109/ACSAT.2013.81-IEEE*
- [15] Bendi Venkata Ramana¹, Prof. M. Surendra Prasad Babu, Prof. N. B. Venkateswarlu "A Critical Study of Selected Classification Algorithms for Liver Disease Diagnosis - (IJDMS), Vol.3, No.2, May 2012
- [16] Sumedh Sontakke, Jay Lohokare, Reshul Dani, "Diagnosis of Liver Diseases using Machine Learning" *International Conference on Emerging Trends & Innovation in ICT (ICEI) Feb 3-5, 2017*
- [17] Heba Ayeldeen, Olfat Shaker, Ghada Ayeldeen, Khaled M. Anwar "Prediction of Liver Fibrosis stages by Machine Learning model: A Decision Tree Approach", *Electronic ISBN: 978-1-4673-9669-IEEE-2016* <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICoCS.2015.7483212>.
- [18] Somaya Hashem, Gamal Esmat, Wafaa Elakel, Shahira Habashy, Safaa Abdel Raouf¹, Mohamed Elhefnawi, Mohamed El-Adawy, Mahmoud ElHefnawil "Comparison of Machine learning approaches for Prediction of advanced Liver Fibrosis in Chronic Hepatitis C Patients", *IEEE 2016* <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCBB.2017.2690848>.